

Dissemination of the temperature-related human mortality product

The image shows a screenshot of the HeatHealth.eu website. At the top left is the HeatHealth.eu logo, which consists of a stylized flame inside a circle, with the text 'HeatHealth.eu' and 'European Heat Health System' below it. To the right of the logo is a banner for 'Climate-fit city presents: MAKING CLIMATE SERVICES A REALITY IN EUROPE'. Below the banner is the 'GLOBAL HEAT HEALTH INFORMATION NETWORK' logo, which is a stylized globe made of dots, with the text 'GLOBAL HEAT HEALTH INFORMATION NETWORK' and 'Climate-fit.city' below it. To the right of the logo is a navigation menu with links: Home, About, Our services, Tools for cities, What's new?, Work with us, Get in touch. Below the navigation menu is a section titled 'HEAT AND HEALTH' with the headline 'Extreme heat is a silent emergency.' and a paragraph: 'Billions of people are at risk of preventable death and illness from extreme heat. The Global Heat Health Information Network is helping to increase awareness and capacity to better manage and adapt to the health risks of dangerously hot weather in a changing climate.'

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About this document

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Summary for publication

In Blue-Action, we developed a prototype climate service of temperature-attributable mortality (deliverables D5.7-D5.9). Due to the complexity of the epidemiological associations to be modelled for the development of the service, we focused our work onto the study of the predictability of the health forecasts, in order to ensure that the scheme generates valuable information that can be used by stakeholders.

The present deliverable is focused on the dissemination of the service. Apart from basic visibility of the work done, the main underlying aim of this deliverable is to attract scientists and meteorological agencies that might be interested in turning the prototype into operation mode.

While the results of this Blue-Action case study are relevant for decision-making, it is also vital to raise awareness about the risks of ambient temperatures for public health. Our dissemination activities focused onto the following audiences:

- the scientific community, with scientific documents (e.g. deliverables, papers, etc.) thoroughly detailing the methodology and results of the case study;
- decision-makers and the general public, by developing a website (<http://www.heathealth.eu>) in order to provide information that can be understood by a non-specialist audience, using easier terminology, diagrams, illustrations, and providing a description of the context and of the state-of-the-art in the fields of climate variability, climate change and human health.

In our dissemination activities, emphasis has been placed on the usefulness of the product for stakeholders and public health agencies in Europe, and under what conditions this product can be implemented to improve the quality of life of European citizens and of the European society.

Work carried out

We created the www.heathealth.eu website to present the methodology and the results of our case study in a user-friendly language aimed at a broader audience. A first version of the website was operational in August 2019.

In the current version of the website, we have made available the results of our analysis studying the predictability of temperature-attributable mortality in Europe at regional scale using weather forecasts with lead times of up to 15 days. The plan is to keep the pages up to date for a time longer than the Blue-Action project lifetime, and update the website with new results, either from the current prototype for research purposes, or from real-time forecasts from an eventual future operational version driven by weather and subseasonal-to-seasonal climate forecasts.

We purposely designed the website as simple as possible, in order to be accessible for a broad audience, and to allow users to move easily through the sections and follow up on the concepts presented. It is divided into different sections with chunks of text explaining the purpose of the project, the study

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methodology and the results obtained, always accompanied by supporting images for a better understanding of the concepts that we want to communicate.

The website is structured in the following sections:

- Home: Short introduction to the service and the strengths of a potential early warning system.
- Rationale: This part explains the background and motivation for our analysis. We highlight the importance of the health risks associated with ambient temperature, and discuss how health early warning systems, being useful tools to reduce the impact of temperature on health, are subject to improvement that we try to address with our analysis.
- Method: Here we broadly describe the methodology, following the step-by-step procedure. We briefly explain the stages of our analysis; 1st stage: downloading weather forecasts, 2nd stage: fitting of the epidemiological models and 3rd stage: generation of health forecasts. In each of these steps we focus on highlighting the benefits of our choices for our study, such as the model and data selection for example. Our objective is that the visitor understands the tools and the system used to develop the product, but we do not go into much detail presenting the technicalities, since we do not consider it the objective of the website. All this information is available in the Blue-Action deliverable D5.9.
- Results: In this section we present the results of the project. We show that the predictability of temperature can be transformed into predictability of temperature-attributable mortality. We mainly rely on charts and maps, which should be more attractive to a wider audience, and which help to see more clearly the differences found by regions and seasons in Europe. We also decided to keep it simple, presenting only the most relevant results.
- Resources: A complete list of scientific articles consulted for the analysis has been prepared. These can be very handy for the reader interested in delving more into the subject.
- Team: This page contains information about the researchers involved in the case service.
- Contact: It includes contact details of ISGlobal in case visitors want to get in touch with those responsible for the project.

Main results achieved

Since we released the first version of the website we have been disseminating the project and the website in different scenarios to people in many sectors that have expressed their interest in our product.

The website was presented in a poster session in the **31st Annual Conference of the International Society for Environmental Epidemiology (ISEE 2019)**, organised in Utrecht (the Netherlands) in August 2019. This event gathered people from a wide range of disciplines, including public health and epidemiology, environmental policy making, climate change, and urban planning among others. At that

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point we did not have any final results, but we could see the interest of people in the methodology we were using and the possible benefits of our climate service.

Also we got positive feedback in regards to the implication of our study for other European projects. We were part of the **Heat and Health case service in the H2020 Climate-fit.city project** <https://climate-fit.city/>. The final assembly of the project was held in November 2019 in Brussels. We had the opportunity to share other work such as the www.heathealth.eu website and the progress in Blue-Action with experts from many areas of interest (building energy efficiency, emergency and urban planning).

On 13-14 November 2019, we participated in the conference “**Making Climate Services a Reality in Europe**”, where we showed the website along with some results about the modelling of heat-health risks. More than 100 climate researchers, policy-makers and industry experts, as well as city and regional actors attended this event to showcase how climate data can serve cities, regions and businesses. Link to the event: <https://www.climateservices.biz/>

In addition, the heathealth.eu website is included in the **Global Heat Health Information Network** (<https://ghhin.org/>), an independent, voluntary, and member-driven forum of scientists, practitioners, and policy makers focused on improving capacity to protect populations from the avoidable health risks of extreme heat in our changing climate. This platform includes more than 400 heat- health resources between publications, posters, action plans and case studies all around the world.

The results related to this case study have been published in the **Horizon Results Platform**, with a specific entry on “Prediction of temperature-attributable mortality in Europe using weather forecasts with lead times up to 15 days”. This is considered a key exploitable result relevant for policy making for the EC policy areas of: Climate action, Environment, Public health. With this Key Exploitable Result, we intend to raise awareness and possibly influence policy but also seek for collaborations. These results are relevant for decision-making, but it is also vital to raise awareness about the risks of ambient temperatures for public health. We especially need collaboration of scientists and meteorological agencies that might be interested in turning the prototype into operational mode. The current prototype can be upgraded for research purposes, or strengthened with real-time forecasts from an eventual future operational version driven by weather and subseasonal-to-seasonal climate forecasts.

Target audiences we address on the Platform are: Public or private funding institutions, EU and Member State Policy-makers, Research and Technology Organisations. Link to the Horizon Results Platform: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform/27065>

For the future, we plan to continue our research on the improvement of early warning systems, which will allow us to keep expanding the results section of the website.

- We have been working on studying regional projections of temperature-attributable mortality in Europe. In this work we highlight the importance of implementing mitigation policies, mostly in the regions where higher heat effects are projected under high-emission scenarios.

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- It is important that these results reach the sectors that can implement our proposed early warning systems. The final aim is to make this service operational, but for this, we need a meteorological agency as a partner. We plan to partner with meteorological and health agencies that can make operational the systems presented in the www.heathealth.eu website, by providing temperature forecasts that could be translated into health forecasts by means of the epidemiological models that we developed. We are currently exploring possibilities to partner with the Danish Meteorological Institute.

Impact

This work has contributed to the expected impacts of Blue-Action;

- **Improve stakeholders' capacity to adapt to climate change:** Key stakeholders' capacity to adapt will be enhanced by testing the delivering of new services to the health sector.
- **Contribute to better servicing the stakeholders that rely on improved forecasting capacity** testing the value of improved climate services for the health sector.

Lessons learned and Links built

We plan to further develop what we have learnt from Blue-Action in the EARLY-ADAPT ("Signs of Early Adaptation to Climate Change") project, the European Research Council Consolidator Grant (ERC CoG) awarded to Dr. Joan Ballester. This project is running from 1 December 2020 to 30 November 2025. We expect this to be a project of high impact, and to give us the opportunity to meet people in key sectors that could be interested in the www.heathealth.eu service.

Contribution to the top level objectives of Blue-Action

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives and specific goals indicated in the Description of the Action:

- **Objective 1 Improving long range forecast skill for hazardous weather and climate events**
- **Objective 7 Fostering the capacity of key stakeholders to adapt and respond to climate change and boosting their economic growth by developing and delivering valued climate services**
- **Objective 8 Transferring knowledge to a wide range of interested key stakeholders** by engaging with the scientific community, policy and decision makers, and governmental organisations in a dialogue allowing exploitation of our results, and providing free and open access and re-use of all data.

Dissemination and exploitation of Blue-Action results

Dissemination activities

Joan Ballester intervened and moderated the session on “Health” at the event Climate Conference “Making Climate Services a Reality” on 13-14 November 2019. The session dealt with issues such as the physical environment, natural factors such as climate and geography, as key determinants of population health and health inequalities and opened an exchange on the understanding of how climate conditions such as heat waves directly or indirectly impact human lives drives the development of health strategies and actions plans.

Link: https://docs.wixstatic.com/ugd/61f9ed_c92c70bd84ff43f48fefb48f7481ec96.pdf

Uptake by the targeted audiences

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public (PU).

The deliverable is made available to the world via [CORDIS](#) and [OpenAIRE](#).

The results of this case study have been made available in the [Horizon Results Platform](#).